

FIELD MONITORING OF CORROSION RESISTANCE IN BRIDGE DECK REINFORCING STEEL

by Yoon-Si Lee, Brent Phares, Terry Wipf and Faris Malhas

Synopsis: This paper presents a portion of a project that investigated the use of corrosion resistant reinforcing steel in the deck slab of two newly constructed 83.5 m (274 ft) x 12.0 m (39.37 ft) prestressed concrete girder bridges. The decks of the two bridges were constructed with two different types of steel; one with Micro-composite Multi-structural Formable Steel reinforcing steel, and the other with epoxy-coated mild reinforcing steel. During the construction of the bridges, embeddable sensors were installed on selected reinforcing steels in the bridge decks to identify signs of corrosion initiation and severity. Using a conventional voltmeter, data were recorded, by measuring DC voltage and DC current, periodically to assess and compare the performance, in terms of corrosion resistance, of the two different types of reinforcing steel. After approximately three years of monitoring, the field evaluation data indicated that no significant corrosion activity was observed in either bridge deck. Although it may require numerous years of monitoring to make a valid assessment, it is expected that continued monitoring and evaluation would provide evidence of the corrosion resistance in the bridge deck reinforcing steel.

Keywords: Corrosion Monitoring – Field monitoring – Prestressed Concrete – Reinforcing Steel

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INTRODUCTION

Reinforcing steel corrosion is the most costly form of deterioration and causes prevalent challenges for reinforced concrete bridges. In the United States, maintenance and replacement costs for deficient bridge decks are measured in billions of dollars¹. This problem has increased significantly and is likely to continue getting worse. Although corrosion of the reinforcing steel is not the only cause of all structural deficiencies, its contribution is so significant that it has become one of the biggest major concerns and has reached alarming proportions in various parts of the world. It was recognized in the mid 1970s that even a small amount of chloride from deicing salts could cause serious disruptive effects on steel members in concrete. The chemical attack, in fact, besides reducing the effective steel cross-section causes cracking and delamination of concrete cover, with obvious consequences on the structure. However, the use of deicing salts on the road is not likely to decrease. Since inspection of reinforcing steel embedded in a concrete structure cannot be done easily, the presence of corrosion cannot usually be detected until the problem becomes significant. While early detection of corrosion within reinforced concrete structures would provide engineers with an opportunity to remedy the problem, this alone will not abate the nature of the problem. Mitigating or even eliminating the corrosion induced deterioration of reinforced concrete structures requires innovative solutions. Over the last three decades, bridge engineers have tried numerous techniques for corrosion protection in bridge decks, including increased concrete cover depth and the application of epoxy coating over the reinforcing steel². Increasing concrete cover depth, however, increases both dead load and construction costs and is in general unnecessary for structural reasons. In addition, although the application of epoxy coatings may limit the exposure of the steel to chlorides, oxygen, and moisture and add minimal costs to bridge construction, cracked epoxy coating in combination with high chloride concentrations may result in corrosion of the reinforcing steel, which in turn affects the overall performance of the bridge. Further, it is believed that epoxy coatings in aging bridge decks may become brittle and eventually, under high chloride concentration, delaminate from the reinforcing steel³.

In the recent past, the use of reinforcing steel with enhanced corrosion-resistance, such as Micro-composite Multi-structural Formable Steel (MMFX) reinforcement, has been considered as an alternative protective measure against corrosion. MMFX reinforcing steel is a relatively new form of corrosion resistant steel with higher mechanical properties than conventional reinforcing steel⁴. While MMFX reinforcing steel appears to be a good option, availability of study on its actual corrosion performance and cost-effectiveness, other than what has been advertised and published by the manufacturer, is limited. In an effort to address this concern, a dual-phase investigation was conducted that included both a laboratory test and a field monitoring. The laboratory investigation consisted of (1) accelerated corrosion tests on MMFX, epoxy-coated, and uncoated reinforcement to determine the initiation of corrosion and the rate of corrosion growth, and (2) traditional mechanical property tests to establish the basic mechanical/structural properties on MMFX reinforcing steel. The results of the laboratory investigation can be found in the reference given⁵. This paper presents the field monitoring portion of the study that investigated corrosion performance of reinforcing steel in the deck slab of two prestressed concrete girder bridges. Two bridge decks were constructed with two different types of reinforcing steel; one with MMFX reinforcing steel, and the other with epoxy-coated mild reinforcing steel. The primary objective of the field investigation was to monitor and evaluate the corrosion resistance of MMFX and conventional epoxy coated reinforcing steels. The overall field monitoring investigation consisted of construction documentation, and during- and post-construction monitoring of two side-by-side bridges. Embeddable sensors were installed, during construction, on selected reinforcing steels and periodic measurements were made to assess the corrosion performance of the two different reinforcing steels.

Comparison study on MMFX and other conventional reinforcing steels

MMFX microcomposite reinforcing steel⁴ has been publicized as a proprietary chemical composition material with a unique microstructure with enhanced corrosion resistance characteristics and higher yield and tensile strength than conventional ASTM A 615 steel. It was designed to delay corrosion initiation and slow corrosion after initiation. With no previously published study available on MMFX steel performance, a project⁶ was conducted by the University of Kansas Center for Research to evaluate the performance of MMFX steel with a major emphasis drawn into the comparison of corrosion resistance of MMFX steel, conventional steel, and epoxy coated steel. This study was conducted in cooperation with the FHWA, the Kansas DOT, the South Dakota DOT, and the National Science Foundation. The rapid macrocell test was utilized as the principal evaluation test. The complete evaluation involves the corrosion testing, the measurement of reinforcing steel deformation, the analysis of material composition, and the impact of reinforcing steel properties on the structural performance of bridge decks. Also, the results of the corrosion evaluation are supplemented with the construction and maintenance experience in South Dakota and other states in evaluating the impact on the life expectancy and cost effectiveness of concrete decks. From physical and

mechanical tests, several drawbacks were encountered in the implementation phase where MMFX steel was used in trial designs for three bridge decks in South Dakota. It was found from the design phase that MMFX provides few satisfactory options for replacing conventional reinforcing steel under current AASHTO design procedures; it exceeds maximum allowable steel and concrete stresses, violates crack control and fatigue provisions, and exceeds the maximum allowable percentage of reinforcement. From laboratory corrosion testing, the epoxy coated steel was found to be more effective in corrosion performance than the MMFX steel. The MMFX steel appeared to corrode when exposed to the environment but not in contact with concrete or submerged in water. It was also found that the mechanical properties provided by manufacturer were somewhat higher than what was resulted from a series of tests conducted by the Kansas DOT. These discrepancies are presented in Table 1.

Corrosion process

Corrosion rate is a function of the availability of oxygen and moisture, and the type and variability of the environment. The actual process of corrosion is electrochemical, which is similar to a battery. Corrosion leads to a flow of electrons from an anode site (where corrosion occurs) to a cathode site (where no corrosion occurs) on a corrodible surface. Two essential elements are needed to allow corrosion reactions to take place, oxygen and moisture. Corrosion will not occur in the absence of either. Ferrous ions and liberating electrons are formed when irons at the anode dissolves in pore water⁷. They travel through the reinforcing steel to the cathode and react with water and oxygen to form hydroxyl ions, after which the ferrous ions react further with oxygen and water to form solid corrosion products known as rust. Corrosion is the result of the electrochemical process that takes place in two sub-steps⁸ as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Corrosion in reinforced concrete

While steel reinforcement is widely used in concrete structure as a cost effective construction material, steel degradation due to corrosion has become a major concern. It is well known that concrete has an abundant amount of calcium hydroxide and relatively small amounts of alkali elements such as sodium and potassium. This presence of high calcium hydroxide and low alkali elements gives concrete a very high alkalinity. According to the study conducted by Hausmann⁹, concrete has pH values typically in the range of 12 to 13, which gives enough alkalinity to provide steel with a protective environment by forming a thin film of passivating iron oxide on the surface of the steel member (transformation of surface layer of the embedded steel to a tightly adhering film). Corrosion of steel in concrete is caused by the breakdown of the natural passivity due to either carbonation, or chloride attack¹⁰. If the condition of reinforcing steel in the concrete is ideal, the steel tends to passivate and display negligible corrosion rates. In other words, as long as this passivating film is not disturbed, it will maintain the steel's passive state and, thus, protect from corrosion. In reality, however, corrosion will eventually be initiated as a consequence of the breakdown of the passivating film unless the passivation layer on the surface of the reinforcement is regenerated. The two most common causes of steel corrosion are chloride induced corrosion and carbonation. The chloride induced reinforcing steel corrosion can be referred to as a localized breakdown of the passive film on the steel caused by a presence of chloride ions. For example, when deicing salts are used on a reinforced concrete deck, chloride ions from the deicing salts penetrate into the concrete through cracks or pores in the hydrated cement paste. The chloride ions will eventually contact the steel and accumulate to a certain concentration level that, in turn, leads to disruption of the protective film and initiates corrosion. Corrosion can be also initiated even in the absence of chloride ions (i.e., through carbonation). Carbonation can be referred to as a general breakdown of passivity caused by the surrounding acidic environment that leads to a process where carbon dioxide from the air mixes with water in the concrete pores and removes the passivating layer. This results in a decrease of the alkalinity (pH as low as 8.5), thereby allowing corrosion to begin. Relatively rapid deterioration of reinforcing steel in the bridge deck may occur due to corrosion cells created by potential differences between steel contaminated with chloride and steel uncontaminated. Corrosion of reinforcing steel results in an expansion of voluminous corrosion products that become five to ten times the original volume of the consumed steel. This increase will generate considerable internal pressures on the surrounding concrete and the protective concrete cover, as a consequence, will be compromised. This would eventually result in cracking and spalling of the concrete surface. Corrosion damage will eventually affect the load bearing capacity of a structure and, thereby, its remaining service life will be decreased.

Corrosion monitoring techniques

Corrosion monitoring techniques for reinforced concrete structures have been well established and known to public, including half-cell potential monitoring, macro-cell corrosion monitoring, chloride electrode monitoring, and chloride-ion concentration monitoring. Due to the fact that corrosion is an electrochemical process, monitoring and interpretation of measured data do not normally require special skills. The electrons, which are released as a product

of the anode chemical reaction, flow from the site of corrosion (anode) to a non-corroding site (cathode). This process allows for corrosion risk and corrosion rate to be evaluated through the measurements with electronic devices (e.g., voltmeter). Among the various possible techniques, the use of silver-silver chloride electrode allows one to measure the potential difference between the silver electrode and the anode steel reinforcement, which is, dictated by Faraday's laws, a result of the relationship between dissimilar metals in the presence of an acidic or alkaline substance. The electrochemical process of corrosion induces current through the flow of free electrons. The electrode produces an independent current as a function of the difference of the metals, the amount of moisture, chlorides present, etc. The two processes are additive. Since both the induced voltage and current can be measured, one may monitor and determine onset of corrosion and its growth rate once it starts. Because of this reason, silver-silver chloride electrode was chosen to be a viable, permanently embeddable sensor for the long-term monitoring of bridge deck reinforcing steel.

CONSTRUCTION AND DESCRIPTION OF BRIDGE

The subject bridges as shown in Fig. 2 are located on US 20 over South Beaver Creek in Grundy County, Iowa. The twin bridges are three-span pre-stressed girder bridges with 83.5 m (274 ft) in total length consisting of two 24.75 m (81.20 ft) end spans and a 34 m (111.55 ft) center span. The primary members of the bridges consist of six pre-stressed concrete beams spaced at 2,200 mm (7.22 ft) on center. A general framing plan and typical cross-section of the subject bridges can be seen in Fig. 3. The bridge deck is a nominal 200-mm (1-in.) thick cast-in-place, reinforced concrete slab that includes a 13-mm (1/2-in.) integral wearing surface. The roadway width is 12 m (39.37 ft) allowing two traffic lanes with a narrow shoulder on each side. The decks of the two bridges were constructed with two different types of reinforcing steel; MMFX steel in the eastbound bridge, referred to as 'MMFX bridge,' and epoxy coated steel in the westbound bridge, referred to as 'Epoxy bridge.' There was essentially no difference in how these two bridges were constructed. The top transverse reinforcing steel was placed parallel to and 65 mm (2.56 in.) clear below top of slab while the bottom transverse reinforcing steel was placed parallel to and 25 mm (1 in.) clear above bottom of slab. Approximately 50 mm (2 in.) of clear distance from the face of concrete to near reinforcing steel was used. All slab and diaphragm reinforcing steels were tied in place and adequately supported before the deck concrete was poured. The pier and abutment diaphragm concrete was placed monolithically with the floor slab. Moderate curbs were constructed integral with the deck and concrete guardrails connected to the curbs.

FIELD MONITORING SYSTEM

Embeddable electrodes as shown in Fig. 4 were used for corrosion monitoring of reinforcing steel. Each sensor is comprised of a solid silver-silver chloride wire electrode wrapped in a permeable, non-conducting PVC covering. These sensors were used to monitor reinforcing steel in concrete deck for the onset of corrosion, cessation of corrosion, and intensity of corrosion growth. The use of these embeddable sensors offers an ability to monitor an interior state of a structure by measuring parameters that can be used as an indicator of the likelihood of corrosion in the surrounding area. Although the sensors do not address the specific electrochemical mechanisms, it provides a reliable and cost-effective monitoring system to measure the basic electrochemical processes.

Both bridges were instrumented with the electrode sensors permanently embedded in the concrete deck. A plan view of the bridge (Pier 2) with the sensor locations can be found in Fig. 5. A total of twenty No. 25 (ASTM) top reinforcing steels (10 on each bridge – M1 through M10 on MMFX bridge, and E1 through E10 on Epoxy bridge) in the negative bending moment region near the eastern drainage points were instrumented. Electrode sensors were wound around the length of approximately 4.6 m (15 ft) of each reinforcing steel. Each electrode was connected to a red lead wire with a protected butt splice (see Fig. 4). A black wire is attached directly to the reinforcing steel using a stainless steel clamp. These lead wires were run out of the deck and are used to measure internal voltage and electrical current to assess corrosion development. On the Epoxy Bridge, two additional short sections of MMFX steels were instrumented with electrodes and placed between other epoxy coated steels (i.e., one on the north side - referred to as 'NO', and one on the south side - referred to as 'SO') to compare with the epoxy steels within the same environment. Figure 6 shows typical photographs of the instrumentation layout on both MMFX and Epoxy bridges.

Monitoring concept with silver-silver electrode

The electrical process induced by steel cathode corrosion is an electrochemical process. Electric potential differences arise when an electrochemical reaction (corrosion) takes place. With the electrode, the potential between the electrode sensor and the reinforcing steel is measured. The electrode sensor serves as a cathode and the reinforcing steel as an anode, thereby creating a "battery". The electrochemical process, on the other hand, is

separate and distinct from the battery formed by the electrode cable (silver-silver chloride), steel, and alkaline concrete. This electrochemical reaction occurs when a local pH value at the concrete-steel interface drops below 9 due to an incursion of chlorine atoms. During this process, electrons are released as a product of the chemical reaction. Therefore, the corrosion site acts as another independent “chemical battery”. These two batteries then become additive to one another and the internal voltage increases. By measuring DC voltage (in volts, V or millivolts, mV) and DC current (in milliamps, mA or microamps, μ A) with a voltmeter, it can be determined if corrosion activity on each reinforcing steel is occurring, and if so, how severe it is. The actual output value depends mostly on the conditions of the concrete after placement. It is normal to expect high voltage levels (it could be over 1000 mV) shortly after concrete placement since considerable moisture is present. While it is fresh and uncured, it is highly active and generates high output. This initial “spike” typically subsides back to within the “normal” range of less than 400 mV as the concrete cures. In general, electrical current readings below 0.100 mA (1000 μ A) can be considered a weak site of corrosion. When corrosion occurs, however, a natural DC current starts to flow from one area to another and this electrical current reading increases significantly; if it exceeds 1000 μ A, corrosion activity is considered quite active.

MONITORING RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 7 and 8 show the internal voltage and electrical current readings for all instrumented reinforcing steels in both bridge decks for three years. All MMFX bridge data appear to be as one would expect; although the data increased above 400 mV (see Fig. 7a) at the initial stage, they returned to normal levels after concrete cure (i.e., the initial “spike” has ceased). Note that even at this initial stage, the electrical current remained below 1000 μ A (indication of weak site of corrosion) as shown in Fig. 8a. At approximately three months after concrete placement, all voltage levels for the MMFX bridge dropped steadily and remained within “normal” range and stayed less than 100 mV. At this point, it appears that there is no ongoing corrosion activity. The epoxy coated reinforcing steels, on the other hand, behaved somewhat unexpectedly. Readings on the Epoxy bridge were higher (about two times higher than the readings on the MMFX bridge) than originally expected. During the initial stage, shortly after concrete placement, some of readings increased over 1200 mV (see Fig. 7b). Although these high data readings dropped below 400 mV, some of readings (E2, E4 and E10) were still above or close to 200 mV. Theoretically, there should be nearly zero readings if the reinforcing steel is coated perfectly; steel will be perfectly protected without any “contact” between the coated steel and the concrete. As shown in Figs. 7b and 8b, however, it is speculated that the “contact” had been made on some of the specimens being monitored. This is an indication that there was at least one or more defect (i.e., coatings may have been nicked and/or scratched during the process of layout) in the epoxy coating on some reinforcing steels. Note that some data show negative readings (M8 and SO). This phenomenon is likely attributed to a possibility of lead wires either connected in reverse or damaged during concrete placement process.

Overall, the field monitoring data indicates that corrosion-related measurements were lower for the MMFX bridge than for the Epoxy bridge. Some of the reinforcing steels (E2, E4, and E10), in particular, showed relatively high data readings. However, no significant corrosion activity was observed in either bridge deck; electrical current readings were close to zero as shown in Fig. 8. Visual inspections of both bridges were also conducted regularly to identify any sign of potential cause of corrosion (e.g., crack, spall, delamination, etc), and no obvious external signs of damage were observed.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Although it may require over a decade of monitoring to make a valid corrosion performance evaluation of the deck reinforcing steel, it is the authors’ opinion that, with through continued monitoring and evaluation, the field monitoring system would provide evidence of the corrosion resistance of the MMFX reinforcing steel under service. Reinforcing concrete with materials that exhibit better corrosion resistance than commonly used uncoated steel reinforcements may improve both the life expectancy and cost-effectiveness of bridge structures.

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Table 1 – Mechanical properties of MMFX steel tested.

Given by	Yield Strength, MPa (ksi)	Tensile Strength, MPa (ksi)
Manufacturer of MMFX steel	0.820 (119) – 0.916 (133)	1.240 (180) – 1.281 (186)
Kansas DOT	0.758 (110) – 0.827 (120)	1.102 (160) – 1.206 (175)

(a) Corrosion process

(b) Reactions

Figure 1 – Schematic of corrosion process.

(a) Typical beam layout

(b) Typical beam connection at pier

(c) Epoxy bridge deck concrete placement

(d) MMFX bridge deck concrete placement

(e) Side view (MMFX bridge)

(f) Bottom view (center span and west pier)

Figure 2 – Photographs of the monitored bridges.

(a) General framing plan

(b) Typical cross-section

(c) Detail B

Figure 3 – Bridge framing plan and typical cross-section.

(a) Butt-splicing electrode corrosion sensor and lead wire

(b) Butt-splice protection with butyl rubber underneath aluminum-foil tape

Figure 4 – Electrode sensor and butt splice and its protection.

Figure 5 – General instrumentation of silver-silver electrode sensors at pier 2.

(a) MMFX bridge

(b) Epoxy bridge

Figure 6 – Typical photographs of the instrumentation layout.

Days after concrete placement
(a) MMFX bridge

Days after concrete placement
(b) Epoxy bridge

Figure 7 – Voltage readings from electrode sensors on instrumented reinforcing steels.

Days after concrete placement
(a) MMFX bridge

Days after concrete placement
(b) Epoxy bridge

Figure 8 – Electrical current readings from electrode sensors on instrumented reinforcing steels.